

Advancing crime-solving methodologies and strategies, and addressing research gaps and future directions: A multidisciplinary approach, to planned crime, espionage, war, terrorism and TCOs, and efficient team collaboration.

Hachmer, J.

Independent Researcher

The Netherlands

Author Note

There are no conflicts of interest to disclose.

Abstract

This article presents a comprehensive multidisciplinary research study aimed at advancing and enhancing crime-solving methodologies and practices. Furthermore, the study addresses critical research gaps, advocates for interdisciplinary approaches, and proposes future directions for crime prevention, investigation, and further research. In total crime solving, we see in planned crime, criminals target, and have firstly, espionage, also, hidden crimes. Then, they respond, and act with a plan, or act on the types they see, with some planned ideas, that will come as a response to seeing the types. There are inside spies, local spies, reverse spies from other enemies, dead spies bringing false information, and living spies bringing information back to report. They would do this because they are having dysfunctions in their personality, they are in a state of crisis, and because of ease of opportunity. Espionage can lead to death and war situations, so the impact is even bigger. The research needs to fill the gap from what point espionage needs to be punished and how, and also, make it equal to comparable crimes when the intent, scale, and consequences are as impactful or even bigger. Compared to other crimes such as killing people, and other crimes that are terrorism. If there is any death it can lead to the death penalty. For example, drug crimes, are related to a drug war, but are also used in wars like IS war and other wars. Drug and cyber wars easily come together, also then IS, and other wars, so, a drugs lab, and drug use are never simple. Spotting hidden cameras, and crimes need community awareness. We will need daily spycam hunters, checking everything, also the homes, and every home, building, and place. Further research needs faster solutions, better solutions, and deeper solutions. Further research needs to find the hidden crime, label it correctly, understand crime, and find strategies to tackle it. Also, it should lead to creating teams that can take out crime scenes and corruption while developing themselves fully against influences and crimes, which help them stay in the worst situations the best. Further research also needs to study the

training of team members and better recruitment, for example, to not hire dark triads, or to have better tests to be sure what types we hire that are capable to do the jobs correctly, without crime, and are perhaps less influenced, and less vulnerable. We can use all the knowledge we talked about in this research to put into guidelines and best practices and create teams. We can train those teams. This can be researched a lot in many ways. We can look at the parts in the total, and create oversight, but also deep developing guidance, changing people by letting everyone become virtuous and change their ethics, so all survive better during these studies and work. Faster solving, better solving, and deeper solving can be in the guidelines. Closing research gaps, finding more absolute truth, narrowing down from correlations to truth, so all can agree, and know what to do, and simply become faster, better, and more deeply developed in this work.

Keywords: Management, self-development, teams, people, forensic, dark triad, hire better, clean workplaces, crime-free, espionage, terrorism, war, TCO

Essence

The essence of this article is multidisciplinary research, or applied research, and a review article proposing future studies and directions. The goal of this research article is to contribute to the advancement and improvement of crime-solving methodologies and practices by leveraging knowledge from fields of management, forensic psychology, but also environmental psychology about creating better workplaces, and safer environments and health science where one also solves corruption and crime to have healthier lives and places to study, work and live in. To create better designs for a better living, solve crime faster, and understand the total work from more fields into a design, also into guidance and further research. Closing research gaps, creating interdisciplinary approaches, enhancing crime prevention, and investigation, and creating future research directions.

Introduction

In total crime solving, we see in planned crime, criminals target, and have firstly, espionage, also, hidden crimes. Then, they respond, and act with a plan, or act on the types they see, with some planned ideas, that will come as a response to seeing the types. There are inside spies, local spies, reverse spies from other enemies, dead spies bringing false information, and living spies bringing information back to report (Web mit, N.D.). They would do this because they are having dysfunctions in their personality, they are in a state of crisis, and because of ease of opportunity (Wilder, 2017). Because it can be psychopaths that do espionage it can also include affected prefrontal cortex, like a depressed state but worse, it includes doing criminal behavior, it is not a normal depression. When it includes also religious war the prefrontal cortex is also a part of brainwashed state activated (Gaw, 2019), and a part is damaged (Azarian, 2019). It can also include an affected amygdala, not able to understand other people, and lack of empathy, and a state like autism, but worse than

someone with autism that would be aggravated, as these psychopaths do the crime, and normal autistic not. Also, the striatum can be affected and this makes them delusional and in another world and state like schizophrenics, those do kill more often than other DSM, but normal schizophrenics aren't killers (Decety, et al., 2013). They do also respond within a week to violent acts if they have seen it and will do violent crimes as well after seeing it (Beall, 2016). Criminals with planned crime target, plan, and hide. They love to target people in isolation, and at night. They carefully pick out targets, and it is not per se personal, it is a type they see, a situation they see, but they do target (Azumah, et al., 2020). They are also able to come out, as they get triggered (Sariaslan et al., 2016), but the first part of crime spying, espionage, or diaspora spying (Government, 2022), is a hidden crime, where one can take them out mostly, as that's most illegal, when the intent, scale, and consequences are impactful, because it had the most impact on society. It is espionage, with the intent to, and the scale they plan, and the consequences clear, so we need to catch it there before they do espionage and spy, and when that is done. Also, then, from this point, we see what crimes they can do, and develop, but it will be first some crimes, and perhaps it will not yet work. While one could punish on the intent and the plan, and the scale and the consequences that will have. The plan they will follow, so what they do now, is what they got done now, compared to the plan, which is what is really the thing they mean and will do.

Dark triad psychopaths will only get worse over time (Anderson et al., 2022), and serial killers, for example, will have moments they killed and stop and then go back to killing behavior. Killers can also leave signs because they planned the murder, and had ideas of staging, and leaving a mark (Hagan, 2015). It needs more research also because espionage is not fairly equally punished all the time, compared to other crimes such as killing people, and other crimes that are terrorism. If there is any death it can lead to the death penalty (Carmichael, Ellis, and Brock, N.D.). Espionage can lead to death and war situations, so the

impact is even bigger. The research needs to fill the gap from what point espionage needs to be punished and how, and also, make it equal when the intent, scale, and consequences are as impactful or even bigger. Execution does happen for espionage (The Guardian, 1953; Miller, N.D.), it is considered the top crime when it reaches this intent, scale, and consequences that it is as impactful. It needs always the correct punishment.

It is suggested some extrajudicial killing is not ethical, but this should be further researched as it is subjective. We will need absolute truth so everyone knows why it is naturally so needed to kill some people that do crimes on that level. One could argue it is not fair to kill someone in their sleep, but when it is the killer who is killing by sending many terrorists to the West to kill civilians in the West it is not at all unethical to kill such a man, but it is ethical, to kill them. So, it will need more research to stop discussions and simply know the absolute truth. It is a punishment that will be used besides the death penalty and other punishments for espionage. This has reasons we need to study as it is a logical way how the people before us got to that. There is the logic that espionage is done for the biggest crimes, it is to control a society. From this espionage, they plan all other biggest crimes. It is a thrill-seeking state of war state of mind and tactic, it is about absolute control (Wilder, 2017). Understanding the reason for espionage cant help us understand all other crimes and how to order them, including how to punish them.

Other crime types, other than planned crimes, would be partially planned crimes, unintended crimes, and impulsive crimes. Random crime, which is still something that is triggering them, or some situation that triggers them, makes them go see and respond to that. So, it still has this first part, of they see, and then the second part act. Partially planned is a crime type with also targets and types that are robbed, or other crimes done to. Impulsive, might have some random crime with some trigger and acting on that. Unintentional is without planning (Crossman, 2021).

The next text was used to explain espionage "If a beach was an espionage target, the Russians would send in a sub, frogmen would steal ashore in the dark of night and with great secrecy collect several buckets of sand and take them back to Moscow. The Americans would target the beach with satellites and produce reams of data. The Chinese would send in a thousand tourists, each assigned to collect a single grain of sand. When they returned, they would be asked to shake out their towels. And they would end up knowing more about the sand than anyone else." (Nowrashteh, 2021, p.6). We could further research and fill in the, what do we see, now? Do we see the same? Do we have the same behaviors and some more? What do these other countries do? Espionage comes mainly from foreigners, that change is bigger and especially when one works for the government.

We might create a lot more stories like these that compare the things we see, so people recognize them faster and can learn to report them. We might only count spies from other governments directly send for some things they were caught for as spies, but espionage is getting military, political, commercial, or other secret information, they can use illegal devices like spy cams, and they can track people and stalk. They can also focus on children and try to spot all from the start of life until they work to further influence and control them, so espionage can become so much more. It can become using entire streets, and towns and see all grow up and use that information with crime groups, TCOs, or governments (Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia, 2023). We can write about all the espionage so people understand every part of it, recognize it, and stop every part of it.

We can also name the crimes they do after spying, violent crimes, drug-related crimes, cyber crimes, organized crimes, Transnational Criminal Organizations (TCO), terrorism, corruption, and other crimes. Violent crimes they do, are rapes, murder, assault, and other violent crimes. Drug-related crimes are drug trafficking, production, and use. They use it also to kill and torture people or influence them (National Security Council, N.D).

Cyber crimes, hacking, digital stalking, deep fake situations, dating fraud, doxxing, selling the information they found, taking over accounts, or taking over laptops, going into files and changing them, etc. They also, influence workers, students, and people, and try to be their minds and thinking, changing ideas people do online, or at work (Atleson, 2023).

Organized crime, gangs, mafias, TCOs, etc. Terrorism by domestic and international terrorist groups (National Security Council, N.D).

Corruption, bribery, embezzlement, thus misusing funds from the government, which comes with a Munchausen by Proxy like approach, using people into fake illnesses and getting money for that, even forced with judges, thus with laundry and human trafficking. Nepotism, is favoritism through locals and family members, at work, which is also corruption. Extortion, money laundering, and obtaining properties "legally" but actually it is all planned or still a kind of corruption, with actions and behaviors setting things up, and being corrupt, and frauds (Ballamy, 2019).

This can come with intimidation, and criminals that come live around for this crime. They can harm, also with the drugs labs they built next door. They work people out of their homes, and with corrupt government workers, including nepotism, and with corrupt judges and other workers. These are situations needing a lot of studies, but have the same approach from the crime scenes, at work and the crime scenes themselves, they will target, and even human traffic family members away with lies, as it is very corrupt and with favoritisms (Gov info, 2015).

They create forced relationships, even romantic and sexual. They create an idea alike communism or communism, that one must be forced to have certain contacts, with them and it favors them, but it is against the real will, and it is even forced to pretend to agree, and like it and it is a cult-like, and including many in the crime scenes, and power abuse. It is no real normal individualistic personal private life, where one is respected to be completely oneself,

which includes many different social ways, genders, preferences, and lifestyles. With this comes a lot of brainwashing, and pressure from groups, or locals at work, or on the streets. Also, if one travels and jobs, they can connect with more criminals in more countries in jobs. Set up on the crime routes (Smith, 2020).

They expand this. They also will collect information about everyone one knows and target all of them, and try to play with them in an act against one or use them the same way, as actually, it is a war mind, and corruption and a group wanting simply a crime and groups with war motives (Baltic news, 2023; MI5, N.D.). This will need more research there is not much research on the spies that expand by getting more information about a person.

Not enough changed over time to solve espionage. The army did not really increase their work on espionage, but the espionage situation compared to before 9/11 and after got worse. We might still use too much of the same approach, which means more is needed, as there is more to do ever since (Carter, 2017). So, we will need research on these extra things the armies and other jobs need to do, that really absolutely will solve the problems.

We have a lot to research and a lot of parts to research, also label it correctly, so we can punish it correctly. We will need to close research gaps, create interdisciplinary approaches, enhance crime prevention, and investigation, and create future research directions.

Different wars are connected to drugs, drugs labs, and the drugs war.

The drug crimes, are related to a drug war, but are also used in wars like IS war and other wars. Drug and cyber wars easily come together, also then IS, and other wars (Unodc, N.D.; Lockwood, 2011). Then, including mafias, and Sovjet war, which has ex KGB and army that went down into mafias, and other crime scenes, also for other ex-war, they can be groomed by IS, and others, or down into mafias and others (Waller, N.D.). But there is also a side of Sovjet Islamic training IS, and a side of Sovjet now at war with Russian war. So, it is also targeting a right winged worldwide, and an Islamic war, but also some like to set up two

to have a war, that is also war tactics (Jedinia, 2016). Drugslabs chemicals can use torturous Sovjet chemicals, we need to further research the torture they do with the chemicals which they use now in the drugs labs and in any way would use to torture (Kirschner, 1984). The drug labs can be used to create drugs for the army, or other things like grenades, also, it creates bombs and all kinds of war materials they can use in all these crime groups (CISA, N.D.). But also Taliban and crime groups related to that are related to the Sovjet (Rubin, 2002). A simple, drug lab is thus not so simple. Then, a few around in streets, is not a simple street. A few in a street is already not a simple town, but also not a simple region and country, as they apparently do not solve it, or do not know to find it. Or not see the dangers, or are corrupt. Also, it is with even more streets with a few of those, even less simple a street, and town, etc. Their attack is besides espionage, attacking, students, workers, and all people solving this. Also, it can be more economical and industrial (Hou, and Wang, 2020), especially in some regions where it is nuclear, espionage has been seen before, but those networks were not fully taken out, as they should have, and especially as that and those regions show they have a history of ignoring truth and aren't capable to solve things well (Kuper, 2020), they cause it or they let it and show not a high literacy and knowledge to solve. They show even signs of corruption, and fellow criminality to not help and solve immediately, and could cause big wars, and nuclear disasters, and such can be related to so much more crime. It is weirdly treated as an incident, and as if such Pakistani handled it alone and as if nothing else ever happens there, that will be not so likely. Those regions need to be forever in the tribunals and ombudscycles to clean up those regions and to prevent any like ever again. Working there needs more caution and assistance and prepared work, making sure anything such courts, governments, and jobs locally say will not count. I suggest using a system where some bigger court already ruled about the people working against the locals so they cannot be further interrupted and sabotaged and human trafficked, but can work freely

without any family court or other corrupt ways trying to overrule the ruling government rules, as they might use other alternative judges with some ideas to fraud, so it needs to overrule any judge in the regions these teams work in, and not anything can happen to the teams and their families and contacts, so they can do their work and take out the real issues, including studying every case the judges ever had, and the governments ever had, and the people in jobs ever had. Also, their any network and contacts, as they'll be in contact with criminals more often and that needs to be found and stopped. To clean up those places totally. These criminals would use corruption, and laundry, with courts, government, and jobs, so we need to make sure no one will be ever even in contact with them other than the work these teams come to do and demand the other way around with real immunity, including for their kids and families. This needs to be controlled missions, but also more immunity for whistleblowers and assurance for all that tell on these courts, governments, and workers. So, it does also need a lot more ways so no one can be corrupt and interrupt. Also, the regions where these espionages happen, and happened need to be fully controlled, as any can be part of it, still. Or could have caused it and none shows to really want to solve it. They might try to hide more evidence, and can be dark triads, with a lot of illness. Also, it can be studied how their behaviors are related to regionally more dark triad genes, it could be an example of taught in families to be criminal, including having dark triad genes, and together, collectively raise people wrong, especially ones with dark triad genes, causing all kind of regional psychopathy. Thus, also, further wrong usage of the courts, governments, and jobs, as they are structurally raised wrong, also carrying generally dark triad genes. A case of cannot help themselves, but are very wrong at work, can be. Also, targeting families researchers, and workers that do want to solve everything.

Spotting spycams needs community awareness

Spotting hidden crimes needs community awareness. Also, law enforcement, without corruption, and very knowledgeable, so the people can bring their findings and will be helped perfectly, without any further issues for themselves, simply all will be solved and cleaned up, and life is again well, as individuals that can go back into their own living in privacy and own lifestyles. We will need daily spycam hunters, checking everything, also the homes, and every home, building, and place (Spencer, 2016). It also, needs wakefulness, sharpness, alertness, caution, and all the observation and vigilance, to get to hidden crimes, with technological advancements.

The people need to get aware, but we also need to be good with this in our jobs, and not let it be some situation where one tells about found spycams and is targeted simply because they told about it. Also, it cannot be one will not be able to tell and lives in torture, or is killed. It can also not be that kids or family members are taken away, exploited, or used further by corrupt crime scenes, for speaking out. It needs to remain the individual that lives on the streets cleaned up. Without people in crime scenes or jobs using the ones that tell, or using it as further exploitation by corrupt that will human traffic with laundry in courts, pretending the kids are better off now with them. As that is exploitation and fraud, and human trafficking. So, we need to label the crime correct and stop it, and the corrupt at work and stop it.

Then, community awareness is encouraging residents to report suspicious activities, which can be done with social media, flyers, meetings watching programs about unusual activities, and all possible creator ideas to create attention and create this movement. There is research needed also on these ideas to create awareness, including risk management, as tellers are targeted, but also not tellers.

The research should be very detailed, for example, we also need all the solutions to how any can get to more freedom as an individual when targeted or more details of how to

survive and solve. Also, on strength to hold on and not go down into it. So, it needs more ideas, and complete knowledge of what people can do, and live better lives while solving the situation around them, without ending up being targeted by people in jobs that take over this losing individuality.

It needs more studies to solve human trafficking through courts with social majors, and social courts. It needs to be labeled better what crime that is. They are like crime scenes targeting all studying taking them out of their jobs, and cleaning up those workplaces. They like to pretend they are immune, and power abuse. So, we will need to be working on addressing them, too, while it is actually both crime scenes, when someone in a job is a criminal, power abusing, it is at work and within a crime scene. One in the crime scene and wanting to use the workers, and tries to work among them, but also workers can go down into crime. Power abuse needs to be solved. Also, espionage and crimes, and hidden crimes, at these crime scenes.

Punishing espionage

Espionage is also the biggest crime label and has death row as punishment a lot, and this has reasons, that it is bigger than rape and killing. So, it helps to label correctly what the criminals do. They start with things bigger than the rest of the plan. They first plan things, this comes with spying, stalking, espionage, etc., so they need to be caught for that. Then, there is the biggest punishment, if you label that correct (Carmichael, Ellis, and Brock, N.D.; The Guardian, 1953; Miller, N.D.). This can also be worldwide solved, as it is Transnational Crime Organizations (TCO), thus collaborations can lead to labeling the crime correctly and understanding a boundary is crossed that leads to certain punishment. For example, when it causes deaths, the boundary is crossed towards death row, there could be a system worldwide taking criminals in other countries and putting them on death row there instead of in a country not so prepared for cases that can end in such punishment. This would create fairness

and equality in punishment, and could lead to expertise without mistakes, collecting truth and creating an absolute truth of how this functions naturally and how this should be done, without disagreements as truth would be found. If countries do not have those laws, criminals can seek these countries specifically, too. This could become a fault in world crime, as the criminals would know where to go and where to expand and do the crime.

So it needs realism of laws, labeling it correct, and not pretending it is a smaller crime. Realizing war and espionage is above all other crimes, a war situation, thus legal in human rights to have death as a solution.

There is a research gap between the crimes, and putting correct labels on it, which leads to correct punishment, including details. To get it absolutely true and correct, without any mistakes. So, all see clearly all the logic without any mistakes and see everything easier, but also correct, and this creates no more mistakes in jobs, and simpler but safe work, as all know and will not end in a play these criminals like, that we take sides, and fight against each other. If we focus on truth, we do not have mistakes. It closes the space the criminals have to target us. Also, it brings fairness.

Creating definitions

Also, creating definitions without mistakes could help create a better approach as we would know more precisely what it is, and can label it better and find the correct punishment for the crimes done. For example, the UN has not yet made a definition of terrorism (Carter, 2017, P.15), as it might fear writing it out wrong so human rights cannot be done correctly if one misses a part, one has a wrong response in law enforcement, skipping another part in human rights.

We might forget there is a framework we can find in the levels of crimes. I recognize that lack of knowledge leads to damage, and this damage can lead to DSM, illnesses, or dark triad behaviors and damages like these. So, the lack of knowledge leads to

damage, then those can create faults in thinking and behavior. The lack of knowledge can lead to criminal behavior, and that behavior can lead all the way to war, but thus actually the lacks and illness do. So, we can research the connections between this and criminal behavior, and find out what causes criminal behavior and influences wrong thinking and mistakes, and damages and create a better design in raising and living together or living in general. But from recognizing the reasons for the criminal behavior better, we get another road in determining punishments as well. It can be we recognize sooner it is actually war motivated, but also, that one is mentally ill, or lacking knowledge, causing damage or wrong thinking. Especially if one is raised criminally, or with a lack of knowledge and assumes one should have to do genocide, espionage, and war.

If one is brainwashed, in cults like Jim Jones (Dittmann, 2003), or in war, or in some other life situations where one can be changed into different thinking, one can cause wars coming from this.

It can make a difference psychopaths can be ill, with affected brain areas (Gaw, 2019; Azarian, 2019; Decety, et al., 2013), but also that some might be schizophrenics, and especially they respond to seeing violent crimes especially violent crimes within a week, and bipolar a bit after, but normal people with no DSM as well after that. So, it influences the brain (Beall, 2016). Then, from all these ideas can come complete definitions.

One could be already actually in war motives, and then it is logical next expanding from crime scenes to crime at work and being corrupt, with such mind actually in the war motives, expanding further into extremism and terrorism, into the actual war. But also those who are at war have pedophiles and rapers among them. Rape is power abuse and if we see more of it it might mean we are already at war. Rape is actually, common in war-motivated people, it is a tactic (UN Women, N.D.).

We could thus realize, lack of knowledge and damage are the first parts creating war, or war motive-creating moments. We can also see it develop into war, but it is actually coming from the lack of knowledge and damage. Then, from the moment one is at a crime scene, and cannot think correctly about right from wrong, and becomes corrupt it gets simply clearer that one has worse motives. When one expands into extremism more people can see it. Then, at the next level when one does terrorism, it is simply very clear.

Although some crimes are hidden, even when it is war, it also takes a while before everyone agrees on what they see, for example, that drugs war is a war, and cyber war is a war. These are even obviously also other wars, attached to that, as they use those wars as a tactic in their own wars. Where the war ideas, or expecting war could be sooner happening, when it seems a smaller crime, but actually is war motivated, but we can see terrorism as a development of some thoughts and actions towards war, as well. They mean war, actually.

Psychopaths only get worse over time (Andersen et al, 2022). Psychopaths will not suddenly seem mature and fine, that is masked and acts. So, the same way war could be, as many criminals are dark triads, especially one in war. Also, the right-winged political people have most psychopaths (Duspara, and Greitemeyer, 2017). It is related to a certain development problem and development in criminal behavior. So, when we understand more about criminals, their illnesses, and their dark triad behavior, we might find then a terrorism definition not creating a wrong set of words interrupting the entire human rights interpretation. It thus, might also need research on psychopaths and the illness they have. For example, they show the same regions one has with depression, schizophrenia, and autism, in the prefrontal cortex, the amygdala, and the striatum. These regions are the main regions. Still one with some religious terrorism would have also some other parts active in the prefrontal cortex (Gaw, 2019), which would not be active in another type of psychopath. So, the same as the normal DSM, there are differences between a psychopath and those with schizophrenia,

depression, and autism, even if they have all of this at once. Also, it has some kind of same being in it as well, but they do not respond the same. It is also not just an upset moment as a person with such a region affected, it is criminal behavior instead. So, it is a lot worse.

Then we can see it as ill, also as in the worst state of the illnesses, and complex as it is a few diseases a criminal can have, and as something worse. Then, we also, besides this, define crimes and realize the development and what everything means, from the lack of knowledge, the damage, the crimes they did, and the "out-of-hand crimes", that develops from crime in crime scenes, and corruption at work, into extremism, terrorism, and war, with also rapes and pedophiles doing crimes, and power abusers at that level, of war.

Psychopaths and Dark triads are typical.

The twists, they cause and then exploit, are typical. Being fake heroes, not the good guys, is typical. All want to look like good guys, but a criminal, psychopaths, or dark triads, will use it as a mask. Target because we study and work. Work on creating lies, and create corrupt workplaces, streets, towns, and regions. It is a job they do but attached to war motives. It is not only the drugs war, cyber war, hackers, trackers, stalkers, spy cams, drugs labs, drugs, drinking, terrorism, and religious war, and hatred about religion, lifestyles, looks, or simply attacking females, and parents and families. In both ways, corrupt and in crime scenes. This comes with a lot, like home milking, homes they use simply for crimes, and with the groups coming there, national and international to be corrupt and damaging to neighbors to expand homes and buy from sellers, after deaths they created, or damages they created. Also, the corruption of the people in local government, courts, and jobs. The typical, so it is to expect, is what comes with these types of crimes, and to expect the other types of crimes, when one sees one of these. It is to expect in jobs, as psychopaths and other dark triads seek those jobs, but also will be going down into these connections and will be corrupt. Also, these criminals will seek jobs. They will be typical Transnational Crime Organizations (TCO).

They will be planned, and targeted from foreign countries, with control through spies, espionage, spy cams, etc control and attack. They will influence workers and will be the next-door killers, and they will use their homes for all criminals to use as well, and they will go as teams into this (Khiel, and Hoffman, 2011; Mind Tool Content Team, N.D.; Perri and Brody, 2011).

More ideas about future research

Future research, should be about all the details, leading to the creation of guidelines, good practices, and workbooks that are perfect for cleaning up oneself, so one isn't influenced, used, etc, and can clean up a workplace, and clean up such criminals. Cleaning up the environment, needs the people themselves to be good people and cleaned up, so not influenced, criminal, lacking knowledge, or with some complex illness, they will be not able to do the work.

It will need people fitting that job. So, it needs the correct labels of the job and people that do not mistake. It needs truth and ethics, to survive (Alieva, N.D.; Byar, and Stanberry, 2019). It needs the knowledge, not missing any of the details, and the spotting of these dark triads, and their tactics and know the truth of what they are and do and expect hidden crimes, and expect more correctly what they would do. Also, it needs the correct approaches back as a response, but also as defense, so they cannot enter anymore. You need to be successful, which needs ethics, so you will need ethical people to work with. But this is at work and in crime scenes things to achieve, as it is coming together, and will use each other. You need to expect criminals around as well (UNOCD, N.D.). Good people can go down as well, but also you need to expect criminals will be there play and act, and use any situation (Beall, 2016).

So, you need to be someone that even if you do not live among the crime scenes and hidden crimes, and spot them. That is the hardest part, I think. People seem to wait until it hits their own homes, and then they are taken down, simply, as it is a targeted crime. They

will have studied, and to detail and years, on streets, towns, regions, and countries. They come live next door, and around it and expand to swallow you up, or simply torture, damage, and kill with some tactics it seems it was not done by them. They will spread lies typically the way psychopaths do, and then together, in groups, including spying, espionage, and tracking, and with a lot of criminals, they get into their homes and expand into homes next doors and around in more streets, etc.

It is planned, targeted from foreign places, and in groups, and to do planned things. So, when living there they do the planned things. They also respond, and change to the new situation, but they come with a plan. The crime level is a lot higher, both in crime scenes and corrupt. It is simply part of the tactic and plan. The ego of a dark triad is bigger, the way they act is a lot worse, and more together. They can also be different types because they come from different countries.

They kill also researchers and all people that are solving crimes, as a first tactic (Brougham, and Uttley, 2017). So, we need this in our mission plans and have it as risk analysis, and with risk management. The reality is worse, and more hidden, more planned and targeted, etc. So, we need to realize our ideas will not yet fit the reality of the bigness of their crimes and the ways they work. Also, they have standard tactics to talk to targets and change their influences, in ways, it is clearly war tactics, so they use chemicals to influence, but also the typical drugs groups tactics, and follow, stalk, intimidate and control with spy cams, but also the influencing by trying to become the mind.

This we know, but it is also truly what it means, as they are psychopaths, and other dark triads and criminals in the war we study about. They are so and they come onto us this way. It needs to be put in research more too, so we need more research. We need risk management and more research about that.

They will come with studies they did on us as well

It is this typical study on the brain and how to influence it, which they will do, as psychopaths, and criminals in these types of crimes. Also, typical studies on how to behave (Azumah, et al., 2020; Wilder, 2017). But we can easily spot them, even when they talk clearly in our languages trying to hide they are from somewhere else, as they are typical, we spot the crimes they do. They are typically, also, nationalists of their own countries, or politically involved (Rogoza, et al., 2021) lying to be now a part of the country they are in or part of us, if it serves them. Sometimes even the previous country was just a route and some next country the same as they are now moved from country to country. They are on crime routes.

Also, they can have very typical responses to it, that make it clear, they are from there, with national music, or songs telling with signs, like a sign killer would, previously before the crime spree starts (Bonn, 2015). But they also behave not at all like the country, but as the crime group they have, which they expand with people from other countries, so it doesn't become a real individual loving the country, or knowing things, it is as if they have a gap actually, in time of the country. They lack the time before they stalked the targets. But they'll first use all they collected from other criminals to sound as if they were there from the time you were in the womb and before, but over time you hear the lacks. They work like cults as well, the typical Jim Jones tactics, to isolate people and to eventually kill themselves, or damage themselves or at least follow them. It comes with rapes and worse (Dittmann, 2003). They come with a lot of people in the local region corrupt and pedophiles, but also worked on looking like that and actually are with some past from other places. This needs further research to understand how they use neighbors, streets, towns, and regions and the criminals in it, but also worldwide, or in other countries. So, there is a lot in this work put into using locals and sounding alike and pretending they are now rulers locally or use the jobs with power abuse, but also they simply change files of workers, delete files, and are corrupt in all

we spread, as fascism can be a political preference, or any right winged will be more common, also, corruption, and crimes among them. They have hatred as well. This would need early intervention to prevent crimes (Cotter, 2010).

So, we need studies on it, while surviving firstly, and cleaning up the jobs, streets, towns, regions, governments, etc. It will need in all jobs teams and aware all out there is different or worse. As they like to create a play with the people in jobs, to create some other reality or deep fake, or simply as psychopaths always do, lie and use the people and pretend to be heroes, leaders, spotters, etc. That twist they love even more, so they like to sound like us working against them, and pretend then all is not effective. Etc. It is the mindfucks, the brainwashes, the influences, the corruption, the manipulations, the deep fake, etc we need to realize and know all about, as well. Also, how they will marry and have relationships, and create forced contact, and communism-like ideas, but at least usage of people, including forcing ideas about who must be in contact with, and that should be normal, or norm, which any criminal would, as they want to use people. They need the fooled and entrance. They need to exploit all vulnerable people, and also, people in jobs with power, to have people, and to have access and control. There is the plan, the targets, and then the needs they have. It is never really true and good, it is all acted, and trained on to sound like or look like. Also, some of these, and are easy to get out, because of some effects, they will come out to play, as they are triggered, and they live with narcissism and other reasons why they can be triggered causing coming out to target more, or out to play.

It is thus needed for everyone in every job to be aware, and we create awareness in all streets, and keep privacy and own space, like all will learn in anything about psychopaths, to take back your own space and life, and to not use care frauds to create an idea of all must something someone finds. It has to be the absolute truth we seek, but also take the criminals out instead of letting them use people and feed that play.

Individualism and human rights need to be very trained and highly knowledgeable about without any corruption and usage as well. With people totally targeting it to keep finding absolute truth, and not just be a mindfuck critical liar, that makes it sound as if the truth is found, but the actual truth. The all need to see, we need. All need to be studied highly and to detail, and realize if they cannot, this can be because of regions are bad. Then, this difference between someone's own choices, vs someone using them is needed to see, and to differ between many details and really know the truth about any situation, we need.

Also, protection, for students and workers, but including this awareness, that we do have criminals around targeting, and we simply need our own individual space, living and styles, and develop ourselves as well, if we want, and how we want. Simply without criminal behaviors, which does not mean someone's opinion of when that is, but the absolute truth of when that is. So, we need that also to detail studied, and with absolute truth. We need to create not just correlations but narrow down to absolute truth and find math formulas and understand how the natural functioning is, and not pretend we cannot find that. We need to realize it is working to get all science up in levels, but it is work we can do.

Simply keep going and become better at it, to find more truth. If we found all variables in a situation, or study subject, and we know how each functions, and together, and gain that knowledge and truth and know how it functions together until we know all about it, we have the absolute truth about it. It will then simply be known how it functions. Then, the broader and continuous finding out, to perhaps still find more, is a scientific logic as well, and we will do that in any way, it does not mean we will not find the truth. We will, but we will also, even then, continue to find more truth, or restudy to find out more about it, and check if we truly know all.

In these studies criminals target, and in many ways, sabotage, or stop studies and work, so we need to create laws, rules, and norms so that we are left to be ourselves and study, and

have that endless space, and in safety. Still, we need to know the truth and find the reality of what we study, as a lot is a hidden crime, and these criminals will target any studying it, or working on it (Broughan, and Uttley, 2017).

Further research needs faster solutions, better solutions, and deeper solutions.

I think, all the work against crime and also this type of crime needs to be done faster, but we also need better solutions and improvements, so we do need people researching improvement as well. Also, we need deeper solutions, getting to the hidden crime and deeper problems and solve. Faster solutions are immediate steps, to solve affected areas, and crack down on known criminals. Also, better solutions are to improve social conditions, also the improvement of true individual life, and choices in lifestyle and social life. Also, own virtuous development. We need ethical, truthful people, knowledge and themselves, authentic and human rights, and their own lives. Deeper solutions are changing social attitudes, without becoming the same as these criminals and corrupt, it needs to be, people need access to their human rights, and the change to respecting people as their own individual being, without doing crimes, but also without name crimes, crimes because someone finds it so, while it is simply a hatred for some kind of type, which would mean genocide, actually, one causes. Or other details why it is a crime actually if one labels something as criminal and it is actually not a real crime. So, the reality of crime, with absolute truth, so people understand truth, and not live with brainwashes, or influences. All other research on the topic is needed, but also to include more of all the hidden crimes and corruption and motives, and the dark triad and criminal ways, but also the data and find the actual situations, but still also be safe and have risk management against them targeting researchers, and workers that do solve the crime. I think we need to further research this, and think better, find all variables, more narrowing down to absolute truth and not just have correlations, we need to go further, so we need to be better, deeper and that makes us faster while being better beings and better knowledge, ethics,

and truth will win, the rest failed, unethical companies will not survive the crisis. They will target us, and we need to be fast, we cannot pretend it is not now happening, if we do nothing, they reach our homes, but targeted so all will go down when they are there (Azumah, et al., 2020), we will need to be better if we have more knowledge and better techniques we improve and we will recognize them better, label better and punish better, so we clean up the workplace, the streets, and will be smarter and faster, with innovations, and better grip. If we are deeper, we develop more ethics, survive better (Alieva, N.D.; Byar, and Stanberry, 2019), and find hidden crimes and solve deeper and more so we clean up more deeply.

Creating teams

Further research needs to find the hidden crime, label it correctly, understand crime, and find strategies to tackle it. Also, it should lead to creating teams that can take out crime scenes and corruption while developing themselves fully against influences and crimes, which help them stay in the worst situations the best. It can have evidence, reports, and news stories, supporting the points. Also, further research can include AI and how that can be used to spot hidden crime, but also it can be about spotting and reporting crime. It can also have informants and undercover operations to hide parts of the crime. Also, deeper studies and broader studies, to detail the types of crimes, and why it has to be labeled a certain way. Also, why do these criminals do these hateful crimes, and other crimes, cause genocide, or have such a wish? From what nationalities, "races", or religions, and why do they attack the other types? Also, about human trafficking and the way they use the courts and governments. Also, how that led to more forced labor and forced studies, and problems coming out of that. Also, how they used government funds for it.

Also, creating a complete picture, of the crime scenes, from the start of espionage to all the crimes they do and then the corruption, human trafficking of families through courts and

local governments, that also are raping children and pedophiles and use the jobs, and do drugs and drugs labs with these criminals, where the IS, etc also comes into their lives, and they actually are all part of one big war scene, with many crimes and corruptions and torture and human trafficking, which started with some people in espionage and some people with war motives.

Also, how one can study this completely, including best risk management and safety. Also, further research on how to create such a workplace and study place can be safely studied, also without losing the reality as the crimes are always worse and also with a lot of hidden and targeted crime.

Also label the war crimes they do, while they do these other crimes, and some parts are war crimes, so they can be labeled and punished as war crimes. They use civilians, so also that has to be punished.

International cooperation

Then, it also needs international cooperation, because it is an international crime, too. There can be many problems with fellow corrupt wanting to expand as TCO between countries with jobs, and are corrupt from their jobs, using certain funds, or certain people and jobs, because these are types, they can live anywhere and all countries can have the same the issues. We all can be targeted, and they like to connect in a criminal way, so we can expect the same problems unless they are actively solved.

Also, how laws should change to keep people safer and save them faster, and better. One can find specific domains on the topic. This can lead to international agreements and laws. Or using together existing international laws, and human rights.

Training and recruitment of team members

Further research also needs to study the training of team members and better recruitment, for example, to not hire dark triads, or to have better tests to be sure what types

we hire that are capable to do the jobs correctly, without crime, and are perhaps less influenced, and less vulnerable. But also, legal and ethical training, but also how to create better laws, and change the laws into what actually is absolutely true. Thus also, independence and oversight of what is beyond a government can help and rule, and how people can create ombudscycles and tribunals and remain in their jobs ethical and truthful, and correct. Narrowing down to the truth. Also, broadly a lot of topics, like secure communication, transparency, and openness, so topics that need to close each other gaps, to conclude a safe truth. We can use all the knowledge we talked about in this research to put into guidelines and best practices and create teams. We can train those teams. This can be researched a lot in many ways. We can look at the parts in the total, and create oversight, but also deep developing guidance, changing people by letting everyone become virtuous and change their ethics, so all survive better during these studies and work. Faster solving, better solving, and deeper solving can be in the guidelines. Closing research gaps, finding more absolute truth, narrowing down from correlations to truth, so all can agree, and know what to do, and simply become faster, better, and more deeply developed in this work.

Conclusion

This article presented a comprehensive multidisciplinary research study aimed at advancing and enhancing crime-solving methodologies and practices. Furthermore, the study addressed critical research gaps, advocated for interdisciplinary approaches, and proposes future directions for crime prevention, investigation, and further research. Espionage can lead to death and war situations, so the impact is even bigger. The research needs to fill the gap from what point espionage needs to be punished and how, and also, make it equal to comparable crimes when the intent, scale, and consequences are as impactful or even bigger. Compared to other crimes such as killing people, and other crimes that are terrorism. If there is any death it can lead to the death penalty. For example, drug crimes, are related to a drug

war, but are also used in wars like IS war and other wars. Drug and cyber wars easily come together, also then IS, and other wars, so, a drugs lab, and drug use are never simple. Spotting hidden cameras, and crimes need community awareness. We will need daily spycam hunters, checking everything, also the homes, and every home, building, and place. Further research needs faster solutions, better solutions, and deeper solutions. Further research needs to find the hidden crime, label it correctly, understand crime, and find strategies to tackle it. Also, it should lead to creating teams that can take out crime scenes and corruption while developing themselves fully against influences and crimes, which help them stay in the worst situations the best. Further research also needs to study the training of team members and better recruitment, for example, to not hire dark triads, or to have better tests to be sure what types we hire that are capable to do the jobs correctly, without crime, and are perhaps less influenced, and less vulnerable. We can use all the knowledge we talked about in this research to put into guidelines and best practices and create teams. We can train those teams. This can be researched a lot in many ways. We can look at the parts in the total, and create oversight, but also deep developing guidance, changing people by letting everyone become virtuous and change their ethics, so all survive better during these studies and work. Faster solving, better solving, and deeper solving can be in the guidelines. Closing research gaps, finding more absolute truth, narrowing down from correlations to truth, so all can agree, and know what to do, and simply become faster, better, and more deeply developed in this work.

References

- Alieva, D. (N.D.) *Introduction to ethics*. USA: MO: Webster University.
- Andersen D, Veltman E, and Sellbom M. (2022, January 6). Surviving Senior Psychopathy: Informant Reports of Deceit and Antisocial Behavior in Multiple Types of Relationships. *Int J Offender Ther Comp Criminol.*:0306624X211067089.
doi:[10.1177/0306624X211067089](https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X211067089)
- Atleson, M. (2023, March 20). Chatbots, deepfake, and voice clones: AI deception for sale. *Federal Trade Commission*.
<https://www.ftc.gov/business-guidance/blog/2023/03/chatbots-deepfakes-voice-clones-ai-deception-sale>
- Azarian, B. (2019, January 8). A link between brain damage and religious fundamentalism has now been established by scientists. *Salon*.
https://www.salon.com/2019/01/08/a-link-between-brain-damage-and-religious-fundamentalism-has-now-been-established-by-scientists_partner/
- Azumah, F., Nachinaab, J., Krampah, S., and Ayim, P. (2020). Determinants of Target Victim Selection: A Case Study of Criminals from Gambaga Prisons. *Journal of Victimology and Victim Justice*, 3(1), 93–112. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2516606920927258>
- Ballamy, M. (2019, June 4). Detecting corrupt behavior. *Lawyer monthly*.
<https://www.lawyer-monthly.com/2019/06/detecting-corrupt-behaviour/>
- Baltic news (2023, April 19). Nordic media: Russia expands espionage activities in Baltic Sea and North Sea. *Baltic news*
<https://baltics.news/2023/04/19/nordic-media-russia-expands-espionage-activities-in-baltic-sea-and-north-sea/>
- Beall, A. (2016, July 13). Stress can trigger violent crimes: Looking for events like a recent family death could help to predict when offenses might occur. *DailyMail*.

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-3688460/Stress-trigger-violent-crimes-Looking-events-like-recent-family-death-help-predict-offences-occur.html>

Bonn, S. (2015 June 29) Serial killers: Modus Operandi, signature, staging, and posing. *Psychology today*.

<https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/blog/wicked-deeds/201506/serial-killers-modus-operandi-signature-staging-posing>

Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia (2023, August 4). espionage. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/espionage>

Brougham, P., and Uttley, C. (2017, October 28). Risk for researchers studying social deviance or criminal behavior. *MDPI*. <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0760/6/4/130>

Byars, S., and Stanberry, K. (2019). Business ethics, chapter 1.2: Ethics and profitability. *OpenStax College and Rice University*.
<https://openstax.org/books/business-ethics/pages/1-2-ethics-and-profitability?query=business%20bankrupt&target=%7B%22index%22%3A0%2C%22type%22%3A%22search%22%7D#fs-idm40116755>
2

Carmichael, Ellis, and Brock (N.D.). Federal terrorism charges. *Carmichaellegal*
<https://www.carmichaellegal.com/federal-terrorism-charges#:~:text=Terrorism%20Penalties,can%20include%20the%20death%20penalty>.

Carter, B. (2017). Analyzing the criminal justice and military models of counterterrorism: Evidence from the United States. *Rutgers*.
<https://csrr.rutgers.edu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/analyzing-the-criminal-justice-and-military-models-of-counterterrorism.pdf>

CISA (N.D.). Bomb-making materials awareness program. *CISA*.
<https://www.cisa.gov/resources-tools/programs/bomb-making-materials-awareness-program-bmap>

Cotter P. (2010). The path to extreme violence: nazism and serial killers. *Frontiers in behavioral neuroscience*, 3, 61. <https://doi.org/10.3389/neuro.08.061.2009>

Crossman, A. (2021, August 05). 7 different types of crime. *Thought Co*
<https://www.thoughtco.com/types-of-crimes-3026270>

Decety, J., Chen, C., Harenski, C., and Kiehl, K. (2013). An fMRI study of affective perspective taking in individuals with psychopathy: Imagining another in pain does not evoke empathy. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 7, Article 489.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2013.00489>

Dittmann, M. (2003, November). Lessons from Jonestown. *APA Monitor*.
<https://www.apa.org/monitor/nov03/jonestown>

Duspara, B., and Greitemeyer, T. (2017). The impact of dark tetrad traits on political orientation and extremism: an analysis in the course of a presidential election. *Heliyon*, 3(10), e00425. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2017.e00425>

Gaw A. (2019). Religious Belief at the Level of the Brain: Neural Correlates and Influence of Culture. *The Journal of nervous and mental disease*, 207(7), 604–610.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/NMD.0000000000001016>

Government (2022, February 28) Criminalisation of espionage for the modern age. *Government*.
<https://www.government.nl/latest/news/2022/02/28/criminalisation-of-espionage-updated-for-the-modern-age>

Gov Info. (2015, May 21). A dangerous nexus: Terrorism, crime, and corruption. *Gov info*.
<https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/CHRG-114hhr95071/html/CHRG-114hhr95071.htm>

Hagan, E. (2015, June 19). Serial killers: Modus operandi, signature, staging & posing.

Psychology Today

<https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/blog/wicked-deeds/201506/serial-killers-modus-operandi-signature-staging-posing>

Hou, T., and Wang, V. (2020, August 23). Industrial espionage- A systematic literature review. *Science Direct*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2020.102019>

Kiehl, K., and Hoffman, M. (2011). The criminal psychopath: History, neuroscience, treatment, and economics. *Jurimetrics*, 51, 355–397.

Kirschner R. (1984). The use of drugs in torture and human rights abuses. *The American journal of forensic medicine and pathology*, 5(4), 313–315.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/00000433-198412000-00006>

Jedinia, M. (2016, March 30). IS 'Cyrillic Jihadists' create their own community in Syria. *VOA news*.

<https://www.voanews.com/a/is-cyrillic-jihadists-create-their-own-community-in-syria/3261535.html>

Kuper, S. (2020, July 24). Nuclear secrets: the Dutch whistleblower who tried to stop Pakistan's bomb. *Financial times*.

<https://www.ft.com/content/be09ba7c-b0d8-45e4-aff8-bf01b4aa558e>

Lockwood, N. (2011, December 23). How the Soviet Union transformed Terrorism. *The Atlantic*.

<https://www.theatlantic.com/international/archive/2011/12/how-the-soviet-union-transformed-terrorism/250433/>

Mind Tool Content Team (N.D.). Understanding the dark triad. *Mind tools*.
<https://www.mindtools.com/au5148p/understanding-the-dark-triad>

MI5 (N.D.). How spies operate. *MI5* <https://www.mi5.gov.uk/how-spies-operate>

Miller, S. (N.D.). Targeting killing: An introduction. *Counterterrorism ethics*. TU Delft.
<https://counterterrorismethics.tudelft.nl/targeted-killing-an-introduction/>

Nowrasteh (2021, February 9). Espionage, espionage-related crimes, and immigration: A risk analysis, 1990–2019. *Cato*
<https://www.cato.org/publications/policy-analysis/espionage-espionage-related-crimes-immigration-risk-analysis-1990-2019>

National Security Council (N.D.). Transnational Organized Crime: A growing threat to national and international security. *Obama White House*
<https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/administration/eop/nsc/transnational-crime/threat>

Perri, F., and Brody, R. (2011). "The dark triad: organized crime, terror and fraud", *Journal of Money Laundering Control*, Vol. 14 No. 1, pp. 44-59.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/13685201111098879>

Rogoza, M., Marchlewska, M., and Szczepańska, D. (2021, October 13). Why dark personalities participate in politics. *Science Direct*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2021.111319>

Rubin, M. (2002, March 1). Who is responsible for the Taliban? *Washington Institute*.
<https://www.washingtoninstitute.org/policy-analysis/who-responsible-taliban>

Sariaslan A, Lichtenstein P, Larsson H, and Fazel S. (2016). Triggers for Violent Criminality in Patients With Psychotic Disorders. *JAMA Psychiatry*. 2016;73(8):796–803.
doi:10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2016.1349

Smith, M. (2020, February 28). A brief history of sex and espionage. *Crimereads*.
<https://crimereads.com/a-brief-history-of-sex-and-espionage/>

Spencer, R. (2016, November 17). Seoul patrol: South Korea's hidden camera hunting squad *BBC News*. <https://www.bbc.com/news/blogs-trending-37911695>

The Guardian (1953, June 20). Execution of the Rosenbergs – archive, 1953

The Guardian.

<https://www.theguardian.com/world/1953/jun/20/usa.fromthearchive#:~:text=On%2019%20June%201953%2C%20Julius,the%20Guardian%20reported%20their%20deaths.&text=Julius%20and%20Ethel%20Rosenberg%20were%20executed%20early%20this%20morning%20at%20Russia%20in%20World%20War%20II>

UN odc (N.D.). Countering the financing of terrorism. *UN odc.*

<https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/terrorism/expertise/combating-terrorist-financing.html>

UNODC (N.D.) Risk assessment of organized criminal groups. *UN odc.*

<https://www.unodc.org/e4j/zh/organized-crime/module-5/key-issues/risk-assessment-of-organized-crime-groups.html>

UN Women (N.D.) Rape as tactic of war. *Un Women.*

https://www.unwomen.org/sites/default/files/Headquarters/Media/Publications/UNIFEM/EV_AWkit_06_Factsheet_ConflictAndPostConflict_en.pdf

Waller, J. (N.D.) Organized crime and the Russian state. *Demokratizatsiya*

https://demokratizatsiya.pub/archives/02-3_Waller.PDF

Web mit (N.D.). XIII: On the use of spies. *Web mit.*

<https://web.mit.edu/~dcltdw/AOW/13.html#:~:text=Local%20spies%20are%20hired%20from,false%20intelligence%20to%20enemy%20spies.>

Wilder, U. (2017, June). The psychology of espionage. *CIA gov.*

<https://www.cia.gov/static/30b273c621d0896f13104ff48840b68f/psychology-of-espionage.pdf>

f

